

Article

MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND ALGORITHM FOR HYDRAULIC CALCULATION OF A MODERN HEAT EXCHANGER CONNECTED TO A TWO-PIPE HEATING NETWORK

Citation Shirinov Z.Z
Mathematical model and algorithm for hydraulic calculation of a modern heat exchanger connected to a two-pipe heating network. Journal of Hydraulics and Environmental Engineering (JHEE) **2024**, 2(1). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13369295](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369295)

Academic Editors: Aybek Arifjanov

Received: 25.06.2024
Revised: 30.06.2024
Accepted: 17.07.2024
Published: **30.07.2024**

Copyright: 2024 by the authors. Licensee JHEE, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions set by JHEE (<http://jhee.tiame.uz/>)

Shirinov Z.Z ^{1*}

¹Institute of Mechanics and Seismic Stability of Structures named after M.T.Urazbaev, Uzbekistan

*Corresponding author: ziyomatshirinov@umail.uz

Abstract. Using frictional and gravitational resistance forces, a model of stationary coolant movement through a heat exchanger assembled from identical sections has been developed. The friction drag coefficient is adopted in the form of a one-term Leibenzon representation, which is suitable for describing five hydrodynamic flow regimes. To solve the problem of the distribution of coolant flow over arcs and the nodal pressures of a multi-circuit network, the first and second analogues of Kirchhoff's laws and the provisions of mathematical induction were used. Formulas have been obtained for calculating the coolant flow through the vertical coolant pipes, which are used to calculate the arc flow through the horizontal pipes. Individual results of a computational experiment are presented and analyzed depending on the number of heat exchanger sections.

Keywords: multi-section heat exchanger, hydrodynamic flow regimes, Darcy-Weisbach law, gravitational force, analogues of Kirchhoff's laws, mathematical induction, computational experiment..

1 INTRODUCTION

Large-scale work on green energy is underway around the world. Nuclear power plants and hydroelectric power stations are being built, and energy based on solar, wind and geothermal energy is being developed. Along with this, the development and widespread use of resource-saving technologies in relation to sectors of the economy and in everyday life require great attention. In particular, the transition from incandescent lamps to diode lamps contributed to a significant reduction in the electricity used for consecration. Various household devices with maximum energy savings have been developed and are being developed.

A similar picture is observed in the area of heating residential and industrial premises. The trend of abandoning a centralized integrated heating system in favor of separate, compact, multi-circuit and economical heating systems has made it possible to significantly reduce the volume of energy consumption in everyday life and in production. Design work on heating systems is carried out in accordance with existing standards, which in an integral form determine the volume of heat loss in the heating system. Depending on the methods of using heat and the needs of production shops, two- and multi-strand heating networks are organized [1,2]. In practice, for example, thermal power plants were widely used to heat the working unit, which could provide heat and electricity to the city or its individual areas [2-4]. To ensure the reliability of the heating network, a ring structure was used [5, 6].

The theoretical basis of the methodology for hydraulic and thermal calculation of the heat supply network developed gradually. The first steps in this direction related to the solutions of linearized quasi-one-dimensional equations of conservation of mass, momentum and energy in individual sections of pipelines [3, 5, 7]. Subsequently, the theory of flow distribution was formed [5, 6, 8-10]. This theory is based on information about the hydrodynamic regime of friction and analogues of Kirchhoff's laws. Depending on the law of resistance, which is determined by the flow regime, and the averaging methods used, a system of equations is formed from linear and nonlinear ordinary differential equations or partial differential equations. In addition, the direction of flow in individual arcs of the network is not known in advance. To calculate such networks, the Lobachev-Cross, Vyhandu methods and their modifications for solved such systems have been developed [8, 9, 11-15].

Below we propose a mathematical model of a heat exchanger, which is connected to a two-strand network on one side. The law of friction resistance was adopted according to Leibenzon, which is a one-term representation and takes into account all five hydrodynamic flow regimes [11-12]. Using the method of mathematical induction and analogues of Kirchhoff's laws, formulas for hydraulic calculations were obtained taking into account changes in the leveling height of the route. Thermal calculation of a multi-section heat exchanger was carried out using the Kirchhoff formulas and the formula for the average coolant temperature along the flow. Numerical results of the exact solution of the problem of the state of the working fluid in a heat exchanger related to the quadratic flow regime are presented.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Heat exchangers are made up of separate sections that have the same shapes and dimensions: height h_c , width l_c , internal diameters: vertical pipes D_v and horizontal pipes D_g . To calculate the heat exchanger, the transverse areas of the pipes f_v and f_g , their resistance coefficients λ_v and λ_g , are also required. In addition, we need the diameter and outer surface area of the sections and jumpers, the average heat transfer value k_{cp} of the heat exchanger and other parameters that are used in the process of calculating the pressure and heat loss of the working fluid when passing through the heat exchanger.

Hot water descends from above - from the upper main line (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the heat exchanger, connected to a two-pipe network on one side

The heat exchanger is connected to the main line through a bend and a valve regulator. Depending on the position of the tap, a different cross-sectional clearance of the jumper is formed, which regulates the water flow Q through the heat exchanger. The total length of the input jumper, taking into account the equivalent Δl_p of local resistance, is l_p , the height difference in it h_p , the average diameter and cross-sectional area determined for the jumper are D_p and f_p . The resistance coefficient of the bend (elbow) and crane is λ_p . The spent working agent, through the final section of the heat exchanger, enters the lower line through the outlet pipe, which has indicators l_p, h_p, D_p, f_p and Δl_p . The last indicator is responsible for the local bending resistance of the output jumper.

We assume that there is no loss of water in the heat exchanger, i.e. input and output water flow rates are the same and amount to Q .

It is required to determine the pressure and temperature losses of the liquid in the heat exchanger if the inlet temperature of the heated water is T_H , the inlet pressure is p_H , and the average room temperature is T_{oc} .

First, the hydraulics problem is solved - arc flow rates and node pressures are determined, and then the water temperature values in the design nodes of the heat exchanger are calculated.

Hydraulic calculation of the network is carried out taking into account changes in the leveling height of nodes h and pressure drop according to the Darcy-Weisbach law :

$$\frac{dp}{dx} + \rho g \frac{dh}{dx} + \frac{\lambda}{2D} \rho w^2 = 0,$$

where traditional notations are used [3, 5, 7].

When calculating the pressure drop, we implement a one-term representation of the law of viscous friction resistance, generalizing Nikuradze's experimental results for the resistance coefficient of a round pipe at various flow rates, diameters and equivalent pipe roughness [11-12]:

$$\lambda = \zeta (k/D)^\theta \text{Re}^n.$$

Here, in the laminar flow regime, you can use the Stokes formulas ($\zeta = 64, \theta = 0, \varphi = -1$) in the transitional regime - the Zaichenko formulas ($\zeta = 0.0025, \theta = 0, \varphi = 1/3$), in the smooth regime of turbulent flow around roughness - the Blasius formulas ($\zeta = 0.3164, \theta = 0, \varphi = -1/4$) in mixed - Leibenzon formulas ($\zeta = 10^{-0.627}, \theta = 0,127, \varphi = -0.123$), and in the developed one - Shifrinson's formulas ($\zeta = 0.11, \theta = 0.25, \varphi = 0$).

The upper units of the heat exchanger with $M + 1$ sections as $1, 2, \dots, m, \dots, M, M + 1$, and the lower ones - through $1', 2', \dots, m', \dots, M', (M + 1)'$. We denote the costs through vertical pipes as $Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_m, \dots, Q_M$. If their values are known, then the fluid flow through the last pipe on the right is $Q_{M+1} = Q - \sum_{i=1}^M Q_i$. The arc flow rates through the upper nozzle are $q_1 = Q - Q_1, q_2 = Q - Q_1 - Q_2, \dots, q_m = Q - Q_1 - Q_2 - \dots - Q_m, \dots, q_{M-1} = Q - Q_1 - \dots - Q_m - \dots - Q_{M-2} - Q_{M-1}$ and $q_M = Q - Q_1 - Q_2 - \dots - Q_m - \dots - Q_{M-1}$. The arc flow rates along the lower part are also determined.

As you can see, the total water flow through the vertical pipes is Q . By this we ensured the fulfillment of an analogue of Kirchhoff's first law.

We denote the nodal pressures by $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m, \dots, p_M, p_{M+1}, p_{1'}, p_{2'}, \dots, p_{m'}, \dots, p_{M'}, p_{(M+1)'}$ and to determine them we use an analogue of Kirchhoff's second law.

The calculation begins by determining the pressure drop p and leveling height h at the inlet jumper according to the solution of the above equation. The input jumper has the shape of a bend (elbow). Its resistance consists of friction resistance along the length of the jumper and local bending and valve-regulator resistances, expressed in total through Δi_p . The total length of the input jumper is l_p . If we denote the inlet pressure by p_H , then we have

$$p_H + \rho gh_p - p_1 = \frac{\lambda_p \rho (i_p + \Delta i_p)}{2 D_p \dot{f}_p^2} Q^2 = K_1 Q^\alpha.$$

The density ρ of the liquid is taken for the average temperature of the coolant.

In the lower jumper, the pressure drop is calculated using the formula

$$p_{1'} + \rho gh_p - p_K = \frac{\lambda_p \rho l_p}{2 D_p \dot{f}_p^2} Q^2 = K_K Q^\alpha,$$

where p_K is the value of water pressure at the point of connection of the heat exchanger to the lower line. Here the values of l_p, λ_p and D_p , as noted above, are taken without a valve-regulator. The value of the exponent takes α into account the possible participation of flow Q in the expression of the resistance coefficient λ .

The main difficulty of hydraulic calculations is related to the loop nature of the network under consideration and the unknown flow rate in specific arcs. To solve this problem, we turn to the provisions of mathematical induction, taking the number of rings $M = 1, M = 2$ etc., and determine the values of arc flow rates.

Figure 2. Diagram of a heat exchanger with two sections

Number of circuits $M = 1$ (parallel connection of two sections). In this case, a contour 122'1 of two sections is formed (Fig. 2). The total flow is distributed over the arcs 11' and 122'1. Let us denote them by Q_1 and Q_2 , moreover $Q_1 + Q_2 = Q$.

The pressure drop along the arcs 122'1 will 11' be the same:

$$\begin{cases} p_1 + \rho gh_c - p_{1'} = K_v Q_1^\alpha, \\ p_1 + \rho gh_c - p_{1'} = (2K_g + K_v) Q_2^\alpha. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here and below we use the following notation:

$$K_g = \frac{\lambda_g \rho l_c}{2D_g f_g^2}, \quad K_v = \frac{\lambda_v \rho h_c}{2D_v f_v^2}, \quad (2)$$

which relate to the horizontal and vertical pipes of the heat exchanger sections.

System (1) implies the equality

$$K_v Q_1^\alpha = (2K_g + K_v) Q_2^\alpha.$$

The advantages of our mathematical model over well-known models [5, 6, 8, 10] of a multi-circuit network are that the direction of flow in the arcs is determined in advance so that all costs Q_i have positive values. Because coefficients K_g and K_v are also positive quantities, then we can take:

$$\sqrt[\alpha]{K_v} Q_1 = \sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + K_v} (Q - Q_1). \quad (3)$$

This form of notation in mathematics is accepted for the case $\alpha = 2$, i.e. in quadratic resistance mode. But in other cases ($\alpha \neq 2$) the designation is also accepted $\sqrt[\alpha]{x} = x^{1/\alpha}$. In this case, from equation (3) we find

$$Q_1 = \frac{\sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + K_v}}{\sqrt[\alpha]{K_v} + \sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + K_v}} Q = r_1 Q, \quad Q_2 = (1 - r_1) Q. \quad (4)$$

Then from the first equation of system (1) we can find

$$p_{1'} = p + \rho gh_c - K_v Q_1^\alpha. \quad (5)$$

Formulas for $M = 2, 3, \dots$

For the occasion **M parallel circuits** problem is solved as follows.

Respecting the generality with the previous options, we proceeded from the equality

$$Q_2 = r_{M-1} (Q - Q_1).$$

$$\text{Here } r_{M-1} = \frac{\sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + r_{M-2}^\alpha K_v}}{\sqrt[\alpha]{K_v} + \sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + r_{M-2}^\alpha K_v}}.$$

At $r_0 = 1$ and then the values r_m are calculated recursively.

Let us turn to the contour, where the flows $122'1'$ $Q - Q_1$, Q_2 , $Q - Q_1$ and Q_1 , have been established along arcs along the clock hand.

Let's calculate the pressure drop along the arcs $11'$ and $122'1'$:

$$p_1 + \rho gh_c - p_{1'} = K_v Q_1^\alpha = K_g (Q - Q_1)^\alpha + K_v Q_2^\alpha + K_g (Q - Q_1)^\alpha.$$

Taking into account the new value, Q_2 we obtain the equation

$$K_v Q_1^\alpha = (2K_g + K_v r_{M-1}^\alpha)(Q - Q_1)^\alpha.$$

From here we find

$$Q_1 = \frac{\sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + r_{M-1}^\alpha K_v}}{\sqrt[\alpha]{K_v} + \sqrt[\alpha]{2K_g + r_{M-1}^\alpha K_v}} Q = r_M Q.$$

Next, we determine the arc flow rates for the remaining vertical pipes: $Q_2 = r_{M-1}(1 - r_M)Q$,
 $Q_3 = r_{M-2}(1 - r_{M-1})(1 - r_M)Q$, ..., $Q_m = r_{M-m+1}(1 - r_{M-m+2}) \dots (1 - r_M)Q$, ...,
 $Q_M = r_1(1 - r_2)(1 - r_3) \dots (1 - r_M)Q$, $Q_{M+1} = (1 - r_1)(1 - r_2)(1 - r_3) \dots (1 - r_M)Q$.

Let us determine the costs for the upper horizontal arcs: $q_1 = (1 - r_M)Q$,
 $q_2 = (1 - r_{M-1})(1 - r_M)Q$, ..., $q_m = (1 - r_{M-m+1})(1 - r_{M-m+2}) \dots (1 - r_M)Q$, ..., $q_M = (1 - r_1)(1 - r_2) \dots (1 - r_M)Q$.

Similar dependencies for the lower horizontal arcs of the network are:
 $q'_1 = Q_M + Q_{M-1} + \dots + Q_2$, $q'_2 = Q_M + Q_{M-1} + \dots + Q_3$, ..., $q'_m = Q_M + Q_{M-1} + \dots + Q_m$, ...
 $q'_{M-1} = Q_M + Q_{M-1}$, $q'_M = Q_{M+1}$.

These values could be expressed through r_m , Q , but the above option can be easily implemented in programming.

The same algorithm was compiled to calculate the pressure drop along an arbitrary arc.

The pressure value p_1 at the 1st node of the upper pipe is known. Then for subsequent nodes $i - 2..M + 1$ of the upper arc the pressure values are calculated using the recurrent formula:

$$p_i = p_{i-1} - K_g q_{i-1}^\alpha,$$

in the lower nodes of vertical pipes at known values K_v of and Q_i :

$$p_{i'} = p_i - K_v Q_i^\alpha,$$

at the end of the lower arc, the pressure value at the nodes of the lower arc can also be calculated using another formula:

$$p'_{i'} = p'_{(i+1)'} - K_g q_{i'}^\alpha.$$

We are only interested in the change in pressure along the arc $11'$. The pressure value at the outlet of the heat exchanger (to the input of the output jumper) is:

$$p_{1'} = p_1 + \rho gh_c - K_v Q_1^\alpha = p_1 + \rho gh_c - K_v r_M^\alpha Q^\alpha.$$

- 0.04219, 0.02040 and 0.01254 l/s. It is not difficult to make sure that it is distributed between the vertical pipes in descending order and the sum of the flow rate through all vertical pipes is equal to the total flow rate through the heat exchanger (Fig. 3). In the results for the upper and lower arcs there were differences (± 1) in the last digit.

With an increase in the number of sections, the costs for the vertical pipes decrease, because, as already noted, the sum of the flow rate for all vertical pipes is equal to the total flow rate for the heat exchanger.

Figure 3. Distribution of volumetric flow rates in the upper (1, 3, 5) arcs and vertical pipes (2, 4, 6) in heat exchangers with five, ten and fifteen sections

Calculations of nodal pressures were carried out according to the quadratic law of resistance. The results, in particular from table. 2 showed that without taking into account changes in leveling height, the main pressure drops correspond to the vertical pipes of the heat exchanger, since the diameters of the vertical pipes ($D_v = 0.01\text{ m}$) are significantly smaller than the other pipes. In the calculation algorithm, the pressures in the nodes of the upper arc were first calculated, then the pressure drop along the vertical pipes was calculated, and finally a number of values of the nodes of the lower arc were calculated.

Table 2

Nodal pressure values (Pa) in a heat exchanger with ten sections

Nodal pressure (Pa)	Arc numbers									
										0
Upper arc nodes	111470	111469.8	111469.7	111469.6	111469.5	111469.4	111469.4	111469.4	111469.4	111469.4
The lower ends of the vertical pipe branch	111464.8	111464.9	111465	111465.1	111465.2	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3

Knots of the bottom arcs	111464.8	111464.9	111465.1	111465.2	111465.2	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3	111465.3
--------------------------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------

The upper curves of Fig. 4 correspond to $w = 0.4 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, and the lower ones correspond to $w = 0.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. There is practically a linear change in flow rate along the upper and lower arcs (Fig. 4), since the flow rate at the beginning of the upper arc is an order of magnitude greater than the flow through the vertical pipes (Fig. 5). With the removal of the inlet section, the flow rates through the vertical pipes decrease more slowly and this decrease is close to the exponential law.

Figure 4. Comparison of the results of local flow rates of the upper and lower arcs for two flow options (see text for symbols)

Figure 5. Comparison of the results of local flow rates through vertical pipes for two flow options (see text for symbols)

Figure 6. Comparison of the results of nodal pressures of the upper arc for two flow rates (see text for symbols)

Figure 7. Comparison of the results of nodal pressures of the lower arc for two flow rates (see text for symbols)

In Fig. 6 and 7 show the results of the nodal pressures of the upper and lower arcs for a heat exchanger with fifteen sections. Similar results were obtained for a heat exchanger with five (output 111464.8 Pa) and ten (output 111466.75 Pa) sections (at the outlet of a heat exchanger with fifteen sections it had 111452.13 Pa). A comparison of the results showed that with an increase in the number of sections, the output pressure of the heat exchanger increases. This fact is consistent with the laws of hydraulics [7]: an increase in the number of parallel threads contributes to a nonlinear decrease in pressure loss.

Figure 8. Pressure values at the outlet of the heat exchanger for 8 variants of the initial data, depending on the number of sections in the heat exchanger (see text for symbols)

In Fig. Figure 8 shows the pressure values at the outlet of the heat exchanger with 2, 3,... and 15 sections. The upper final pressure curves relate to the speed $w = 0.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, and the lower ones – to $w = 0.4 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. As the number of sections increases, the pressure loss decreases, which is explained by Kirchhoff's second law: with an increase in the number of parallel threads, the pressure loss decreases.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Within the framework of a quasi-one-dimensional approach, a mathematical model and an algorithm for hydraulic calculation of a modern heat exchanger connected to a two-line heating network on one side are proposed.

When describing mass transfer, the factor of leveling height was taken into account, a single-term representation of the law of friction resistance and analogues of Kirchhoff's laws were used.

Analytical formulas were obtained for calculating the flow rates for the elements of the upper and lower arcs, as well as for the vertical pipes, and the nodal pressure of the working fluid in a multi-section heat exchanger.

It was revealed that the costs of the vertical radiator pipes amount to the total flow rate of the heat exchanger and with an increase in the number of sections, as well as with distance from the entrance to the heat exchanger, the costs of the vertical pipes decrease.

The reaction of the final results to changes in a number of initial indicators was checked. Changes in the values of internal and external diameters, length and height of sections showed adequate changes in results according to the physical representations of the object.

REFERENCES

1. Tikhomirov, K. V., & Seregeenko, E. S. (1991). Heating engineering, heat and gas supply and ventilation (4th ed., revised and additional). Moscow: Stroyizdat.
2. Akbasov, A. R. (2011). Development of an intelligent management system for city heating networks (Doctoral dissertation, Kazakh National Technical University named after K.I. Satpayeva). Almaty.
3. Mirkin, A. Z., & Usinsh, V. V. (1991). Pipeline systems. Moscow: Chemistry.
4. Novitsky, N. N., Alekseev, A. V., Grebneva, O. A., Lutsenko, A. V., Tokarev, V. V., & Shalaginova, Z. I. (2019). Multilevel modeling and optimization of large-scale pipeline systems operation. *Energy*, 184, 151-164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.02.070>
5. Evdokimov, A. G., Tevyashev, A. D., & Dubrovsky, V. V. (1990). Modeling and optimization of distribution flow in utility networks (2nd ed., revised and additional). Moscow: Stroyizdat.
6. Zvereva, T. V., Chelintsev, S. N., & Yakovlev, E. I. (1987). Modeling of pipeline transport for petrochemical plants. Moscow: Chemistry.
7. Shterenlikht, D. V. (1991). Hydraulics: Textbook. Moscow: Energoatomizdat.
8. Merenkov, A. P., & Khasilev, V. Ya. (1985). Theory of hydraulic circuits. Moscow: Nauka.
9. Seleznev, V. E., Aleshin, V. V., & Pryalov, S. N. (2007). Modern computer simulators in pipeline transport. Mathematical modeling methods and practical application (Ed. V. E. Selezneva). Moscow: MAKS Press.
10. Sennova, E. B., & Sidler, V. G. (1987). Mathematical modeling and optimization of developing heat supply systems. Novosibirsk: Nauka.
11. Khujaev, I. K. (2009). Development of mathematical models of diffusion combustion and gas transportation through a pipeline (Doctoral dissertation, IMiSS AN RUz). Tashkent.
12. Sadullaev, R., et al. (2003). Calculation of the main gas pipeline taking into account the terrain. *Gas Industry*, (8), 58-59.
13. Charny, I. A. (1975). Unsteady motion of real fluid in pipes (2nd ed.). Moscow: Nedra.
14. Khujaev, I. K., Aminov, X. Kh., & Mamadaliyev, X. A. (2021). About the results of computational experiments in the study of features of transients in the sections of the gas pipeline. In *Models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research: International scientific-online conference, Germany 2021* (pp. 68-75). Retrieved from www.interonconf.org
15. Khujaev, I., Bozorov, O., & Akhmadjonov, S. (2020). Investigation of the propagation of waves of sudden changes in mass flow rate of fluid and gas in a "short" pipeline approach. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series, AMSD-2019*. IOP Publishing, 1441(1), 012146. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-596/1441/1/012146>